

CONSTRUCTION OF RECREATIONAL INTEREST SCALE: THROUGH ITEM TOTAL CORRELATION ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This paper aimed to develop and standardize the recreational interest scale specifically for high school students. Recreation is individual's favored enjoyable and agreeable activities in which they employ during free time. Interest is an emotion. It is an object or in an activity reveals itself a heightening of attention to it. The feeling of wanting to give the attention to recreational activities is called as recreational interest. The steps followed in the construction of Recreational Interest Scale using Item Total Correlation Analysis were, discussion, review, writing statements, creating an item pool, editing of items, rank, scoring, instructions for respondents, pilot study, validity, reliability and framing of final draft. The investigators developed the preliminary draft of Recreational Interest Scale (48 items) with uncomplicated, obvious, and brief statements for better understanding in Tamil version. The validity for each item was analyzed using item whole correlation. Thus the final Recreational Interest Scale consisted of 31 items. This scale intended to include the information and conceptions of high school teachers regarding the recreational interest.

Keywords: Recreation, Interest, Recreational Interest, High School Students

Introduction

Once upon a time, the home was a self-sufficient organization for the development of recreational experience. In the past, mostly the size of the families was large and most of the families ran under the function of joint family. So that the correlation between every members of combined family were profound and cherished. And also, the family members were executed a variety of activities together. But, now a days, the nature of family is changed as nuclear family. The activities previously penetrated into by family members are now weakened or not present. Urban life style, social mobility, work opportunities, and other social influences have distributed the family generally less effective as an organization for the development of the recreational activity of its members (Shivers, Jay, 2002). So today's school going students interests are imprisoned in technological gadgets. They are not known about their recreational interest apart from the usage of technological gadgets. As there is a close relationship between interest and education, the foremost difficulties in the classrooms are the psychological elements of interest and its subsistence. Every teacher's attention should be on the method of stimulating the interests of their students. So, to make interest among students, the teachers presenting the content in good fashion in the classroom according the students' curiosity. The teachers also desire to stimulate the students' learning efficiently. The maximum support to attention is interest. And also, interest is the emotional part of attention. The concentration and curiosity are appeared in the dimensions of

consciousness. (Kundu & Tutoo, 2008) Apart from students' interests on their studies, their recreational interest also very significant in stimulate their interest towards their studies. Recreational activities are openly selected by the individual. But, Because of the burdens of school tasks, family commitments, extracurricular activities, most adolescents have distant less time for recreation than they did when they were younger.

Theoretical Construct of Recreational Interest

Recreation: Recreation is individual's favored enjoyable and agreeable activities in which they employ during free time. Recreation is subjective in nature but not objective. Recreational activities can be inactive or sedentary in character, like, playing carom board, knitting, enjoying the music, playing musical instruments, usage of social media. It can also be alive or active and improve physical fitness and well being. Examples of active recreation include running, walking, skipping, dancing, bowling, hiking, trekking, boating, bicycling, hockey, and cricket. Awareness on recreation activities among school students affords significant assistance to a extensive array of student abilities in the areas of social interaction, orientation and mobility, independent living, and self-determination. *Interest:* Interest is an emotion. It is an object or in an activity reveals itself a heightening of attention to it. (Kundu & Tutoo,2008). Recreational Interest: The feeling of wanting to give the attention to recreational activities is called as recreational interest.

Recreational Interest of Adolescents

New interests develop throughout the adolescent years in consequence of the enormous changes made during the process of maturation. Recreational interests also undergo modifies during adolescence. Although a great deal of energy is still used in competitive physical activities, there appears to be more selectivity toward activities. Sexual interests are roused during this post pubertal period. The desire for independence comes to a peak in late adolescence. The recreational interests of the late adolescent appear to be even more restricted than previously. More time is spent on fewer activities. There is a gradual decline in participation in strenuous physical activity and immense inclination to be a passive spectator. Social activities, intellectual activities and some hobby forms appeal to adolescents. Those who participate in hobbies tend to seek construction experiences. Reading also becomes an extremely pleasurable form of activity. A whole range of entertainments opens for late adolescents, as they have more money and greater discretion in the expenditure of money on activities they find enjoyable. Attendance at dances, concerts, movies, theatre and the like are popular. The need to earn a living invariably forces a diminishing of recreational activity. There is a consequent narrowing of interests, although younger adults have a more varied series of recreational experiences than do older adults. Up to a particular point, participation in hobbies seems to increase with age. Hobbies offer intense satisfaction, challenge and enrichment lacking in other forms of recreational experience. Hobbies are this likely to present opportunities for satisfying basic needs when the other forms of involvement are no longer open or accessible. Recreational activities of all kinds present enriched living potential and amply demonstrate the need to cultivate constructive and purposeful

experiences of this nature. Children are a product of their nature and nurture. They must have broad parental guidance so that the development of satisfying interests will emerge with maturity and permit the individuals to invest their time creatively, pleasurably and ethically (Shivers, Jay, 2002).

Item Discrimination and Item Total Correlation

Item discrimination is a common concept for evaluating the degree to which an item might affect a tests' internal consistency. Briefly stated, item discrimination is the degree to which an item differentiates people who score high on the total test from those who score low on the total test. From the perspective of reliability, we prefer to have items that have high discrimination values over those that have low discrimination values. There are various ways of operationalizing an item's discrimination, one of which is the item – total correlation. We can compute the total score on a test and then compute the correlation between an item with this total test score. The resulting correlation is called an item – total correlation, and it represents the degree to which differences among persons' responses to the item are consistent differences in their total test scores. A high item – total correlation indicates that the item is consistent with the test as a whole (which of course is a function of all of the items within the test), which is a desirable characteristic. In contrast, low item – total correlation indicates that the item is inconsistent with the test as a whole, which would be an undesirable characteristic from the perspective of reliability (Furr, Michael & Bacharach, Verne, 2008). The item-test correlation is the Pearson correlation coefficient calculated between the scores of one item of each pair is an item score and the other item is the total test score. If the correlation co-efficient is high, the correlation between the item and the total test is also strong. The test developers are tried to choose the items' score who has high correlation with total score. From that the test developers ensured that the test is internally consistent. For the reason that the item-test correlation is frequently employed to hold up the disputation that the item is a “good” donor to what the test measures, it is called an *index of item validity*.

Steps in Construction of Recreational Interest Scale

Recreational Interest Scale was validated and standardized by N. Subramanian and M. Mary Chinnarani in 2019. It was meant for the high school students. For the scientific preparation of the tool, certain important considerations and procedures were followed. There are some universal standard and procedures which researchers to follow while constructing a research tool. The foremost steps pursued in the construction of the research tool (Recreational Interest Scale) are explained under the varied heads.

Discussion: The Recreational Interest Scale prepared by the investigator and guide aims at measuring the recreational interest of high school students. The investigators are informally talked about the issues, concepts and theoretical constructs about general interest and recreational interest of higher secondary students with experts in the fields of Education, school teachers, head masters and teacher educators.

Review: The investigators are reviewed literatures related to interest and recreational interest in journals, books, articles and internet resources. For the generation of the items in the scale, the literature review assists.

Writing Statements: The investigator wrote the positive and negative statements related to the proposed problem i.e., recreational interest of high school students.

Create an item pool: The investigator wrote the items continuously in both positive and negative in nature, until item pool at least twice the size of the research tool intended, i.e., if the investigator plans to have 20 items in preliminary draft, then create an item pool of 40 items.

Editing of items: After collected the items as much as possible, the investigator went through the each and every item in the item pool very carefully. The investigator avoided the statements which refer to past rather than to present, irrelevant to be endorse by almost every one or no one, irrelevant to the object under consideration, more than one thought and double negative statements, certain word that may not be understood by the respondents, certain such universals i.e., all, always, none, never, often etc. as these introduce ambiguity, using emotional words or phrases in items and double barrel questions.

Rank: After the process of editing, the investigators were chose the items and provided rating to the items. Rank ordered the items on effectiveness and precision. The investigators were chose an equal number. Generally, five categories are standard. But the investigators were chose three point scale i.e., yes, rarely, and no.

Scoring: The points given for every response depends on whether the statement is positive or negative. The person who strongly concurs with a positive statement gets maximum points. One who strongly opposes with a positive statement gets the minimum points. For the purpose of scoring, the investigators were assigned the numerical value of 3 to yes, 2 to rarely and 1 to no. In case of the item is negative, the investigators overturned the order of scoring.

Instructions for respondents: The investigators were prepared the instructions which clearly explain how to select the response on the research tool.

Pilot Study: Once the statements are gathered, then the subsequent step is pilot study. A preliminary try out was prepared to discover the smartness and usefulness of the items. The investigators were noted the problems faced by the high school students in responding to the items present in the Recreational Interest Scale. And also they were observed the rough estimate of the time limit for responding the items in the questionnaire. From the above said notion and observation, the investigators were modified some specific technical terms which were ambiguous and doubtful for this purpose the scale was given to students. The investigators were decided to have the items which are uncomplicated and statement is easy to understand for the high school students. The investigator framed the items on three point scale namely, Yes, Rarely and No. The investigator showed Recreational Interest Scale to two experienced Educational Psychologists and teacher educators and to verify the suitability of the items to the target students. After attentive tailoring, 48 items were retained. The high school students were instructed to pick the best operation against the statement by blotting a tick (✓) in the applicable column. The positive item in the draft tool conversely a score of 3 was given for yes, 2 for rarely, and 1 for no. For validating the preliminary draft of

Recreational Interest Scale, it was given to 50 high school students of Government Girls Hr. Sec. School, Puliangudi. In this study, the high school students referred to IX and X standard students.

Validity: Validity is the degree to which the benchmark offers an authentic depiction of what one is attempting to measure. The investigators were used the procedures depicted in the item-total correlation. The row and the column of the table was allocated for numbers or respondents as 1-50 and items were numbered as 1-48 in the preliminary draft of recreational interest scale of each responded were calculated in item wise table. The sum of the scores attained by the entire respondents was calculated individually. The co-efficient of correlation between each item by all the scores of 48 items of each scores was calculated using the following Pearson product moment correlation. The validity for each item was analyzed. The item validity was calculated by finding the correlation between the total score and item score. The co- efficient of correlation between each item by all the scores of items and each score was calculated using the following Pearson's product moment formula,

$$R = \frac{N(\sum XY) - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{N \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2} \sqrt{N \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2}}$$

Where, R = Correlation Co-efficient, $\sum X$ = Sum of X Score, $\sum Y$ = Sum of Y Score, $\sum X^2$ = Sum of square of X score, $\sum Y^2$ = Sum of square of Y score and N = Number of students. The item validity corresponding to the items in the preliminary draft of Recreational Interest Scale is equal to or greater than 0.30 were selected. The r-values of selected items are the following table.

Table 1: Selected Items in Recreational Interest Scale

Item No.	r-Values	Selected Items	Item No.	r-Values	Selected Items
1	0.11406		25	0.2091	
2	0.1437		26	0.4021	✓
3	0.0743		27	0.0377	
4	0.4006	✓	28	0.3252	✓
5	0.2372		29	0.4646	✓
6	0.1138		30	0.2982	
7	0.4449	✓	31	0.4272	✓
8	0.3773	✓	32	0.1621	
9	0.5517	✓	33	0.4423	✓
10	0.2371		34	0.4845	✓
11	0.3522	✓	35	0.4570	✓
12	0.3620	✓	36	0.3220	✓
13	0.4884	✓	37	0.2814	
14	0.4725	✓	38	0.4980	✓
15	0.2006	✓	39	0.1696	
16	0.3300	✓	40	0.1734	

17	0.1386		41	0.4575	✓
18	0.4205	✓	42	0.5171	✓
19	0.5423	✓	43	0.3064	✓
20	0.4282	✓	44	0.3560	✓
21	0.2575		45	0.4263	✓
22	0.2484		46	0.2779	
23	0.3306	✓	47	0.3543	✓
24	0.3797	✓	48	0.4230	✓

✓ Selected Items

Reliability: The investigators were calculated the Reliability of the Recreational Interest Scale using Split-Half method. Thus the correlation co-efficient (r) and reliability co-efficient (r^1) were found to be 0.643 and 0.7827 respectively.

Framing of final draft: The investigators were prepared the neatly printed final draft of Recreational Interest Scale and administrated to the target students to record their opinions. The final draft of Recreational Interest consists of 31 items.

Conclusion

The methodological construction of Recreational Interest Scale through Item Total Analysis and steps was evidently portrayed in this article. And also this scale was intended to including the information and conceptions of high school teachers regarding the recreational interest. This scale will be valuable in the assessment and screening of recreational interest of high school students. This validated Recreational Interest Scale may help teachers, researchers and educationists to examining the recreational interest of high school students.

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